

R̥ṣi-Bhāṣita : A Study

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The Place of R̥ṣibhāṣita in Jain Literature

R̥ṣibhāṣita is one of the oldest works in *Ardhamāgadhi* Jain canonical literature. Under the accepted system of classification of Jain tradition has 12 *Āngas* and 14 *Āngabāhyas*, but R̥ṣibhāṣita is not included in them. The *terāpanthi* and *Sthānakvāsi* sects of the Śvetāmbar tradition also do not include R̥ṣibhāṣita in the 32 *Āgamas* they recognise. The idol worshipping sect of the Śvetāmbar tradition recognises 45 *Āgamas* including 11 *Āngas*, 12 *Upāṅgas*, 6 *Chhedasūtras*, 4 *Mūlsūtras*, 2 *Culikā*, 10 *Prakīrnakas*. R̥ṣibhāṣita is not included even in these 10 *Prakīrnakas*. However, it is included in the list of *Kāliksūtras* mentioned in *Nandisūtra* and *Pakkhisūtra*.¹ The *Āngabāhya* works including *Sāmāyika* and then *Daśavaikālika*, *Uttarādhyayan*, *Daśā* (*Acārdasā*), *Kalpa*, *Vyāvahār Nishīth* and *R̥ṣibhāṣita*.² Haribhadra is the *Vṛtti* of *Āvaśyaka Nirvyukti* mentions R̥ṣibhāṣita once with *Uttarādhyayana*³ and at another place with an anthology titled *Devinduthuya*.⁴ The reason for this confusion may be that besides R̥ṣibhāṣita Haribhadra also came across R̥ṣimaṇḍala Stava which gets a mention in *Ācāraṅga cūrni*. His intension must have been to connect R̥ṣibhāṣita, *Uttarādhyayan*, and R̥ṣimaṇḍala Stava with *Devinduthuya*. It should be noted that R̥ṣimaṇḍala not only mentions many of the R̥ṣis (ascetics) of R̥ṣibhāṣita but also refers to chapters and contents therein. This indicates that the author of R̥ṣimaṇḍala must have been aware of and had studied R̥ṣibhāṣita. The similarity between these two works is so much that with a little

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Note : For foot-notes please refer to the foot notes of original Hindi text.

variation is sequence and names almost all R̥ṣis of R̥ṣibhāṣita can be found in R̥ṣimaṇḍala. The mention of R̥ṣimaṇḍala in *Ācāraṅga Cūrni* (*Isinamakittanam Isimandalatthan*, page 374) conclusively establishes that it predates *Ācāraṅga Cūrni* (7th century A.D.). Scholars should give a serious thought to this fact. It is believed that R̥ṣimaṇḍala was written by *Dharmaghosh Sūri* of *Tapāgachchha* sect, but I have my doubts as his period is 14th century A. D. In fact, the language and style of R̥ṣimaṇḍala indicates that it is an ancient work and its author has studied R̥ṣibhāṣita. In the course of studies of canons for mendicants prescribed by *Ācārya Jinaprabha* in his work *Vidhimārgaprabha* the list of anthologies to be studied has been concluded with the mention of R̥ṣibhāṣita.⁵ As such, according to the accepted system of classification, R̥ṣibhāṣita can be classified as an anthological work.

In the ancient Jain tradition it was recognised as an important work. In *āvaśyaka Nirvyukti*. Bhadrabāhu has expressed his intent to write a *Nirvyukti* on R̥ṣibhāṣita.⁶ As no such work is available today, it is difficult to surmise if it was written at all. Of course, R̥ṣimaṇḍala, which finds a mention in *Ācāraṅga chūrni*, certainly appears to be a connected work. All this goes to prove that upto a certain period R̥ṣibhāṣita must have been an important work in Jain tradition. *Sthānaṅg* refers to it as a part of *Praśnavyākaraṇaśā*.⁷ *Samvayaṅga* has mentioned about its fortyfour chapters.⁸ As already mentioned. *Nandisūtra*, *Pakkhisutra* etc. include it in the classification *Kaliksutra*. *Āvaśyaka Nirvyukti* classifies it as a work of *Dharmakathānuyoga*.

Style and Period of R̥ṣibhāṣita

According to its language, style, and subject matter this is an extremely old work among the Jain canonical works of *Ardhamāgadhi* language. I consider this work being of a period slightly later than that of first *Srūtaskandha* of *Ācāraṅga* but earlier than that of other ancient works like *Sūtrakṛtaṅga*, *Uttarādhyayan*, and *Daśavaikālika*. Even its present form can under no circumstances be dated later than 3rd or 4th century B.C. As per the information available in *Sthānaṅga* this work was originally a part of *Praśnavyākaraṇaśā*; the ten *Daśas*

described in *Sthānāṅga* include *Ṛṣibhāṣita* also. *Samavāyāṅga* infirms that this contains 44 Chapters. As such *Ṛṣibhāṣita* certainly pre-dates these works. In *Sutrakṛtāṅga* there is a mention of ascetics like *Nami, Bahuk, Ramaputta, Asit Deval, Dvaipayan,* and *Parashar* as also little indications about their ritual beliefs. They have been recognised by *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, an exposition by *Arhat*. All these *Ṛṣis* attained liberation inspite of their consumption of seeds and water⁹.

This gives rise to the question as to which work predating *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* has accepted these people in the exalted position? In my opinion only *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is such a work. The term '*lha-sammata*', from the verse in *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, appears to be referring to the antiquity of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* rather than *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* itself. It should be noted that in both *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* as well as *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, many *Ṛṣis* of traditions other than Jain, e.g. *Asit Deval, Bahuk* etc., have found a revered mention. Although these two are mainly in verse, from the viewpoint of language first *Śrutaskandha of Sūtrakṛtāṅga* appears to be of a later period. This is because the language of *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* is nearer to *Mahārāshtri Prākṛta* whereas that of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is ancient *Ardhamāgadhi*, leaving aside a few later changes. Also, *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* has criticised the thinkers of other traditions but *Ṛṣibhāṣita* has eulogised them.

This is a firmly established fact that this work was created prior to the institutionalisation of Jain religion and social organisation. Study of this work explicitly indicates that at the time of its writing Jain organisation was completely free of sectarian bias. *Mñkhali Gośāla* and his philosophy find mention in Jain canons like *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*¹⁰, *Bhagvati*¹¹, and *Upāsakdaśāṅga*¹² and Buddhist works like *Suttanipāta, Dīghnikaya (Sammañjafalasutta)*¹³. Although there is no specific mention of *Mankhali Gośāla* in *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*. *Niyativāda* has been commented upon in its chapter titled *Ārdrak*. Analysing from the view point of development of sectarian feelings, the portion of *Bhagvati* dealing with *Mañkhali Gośāla* clearly appears to be of later period than even *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* and *Upāsakdaśāṅga*. These two works as well as many works of Pali Tripitaka mention the *Niyativāda*

of *Mañkhali Gośāla* and then counter it. Still, unlike Jain Canonical works, the *Sūttanipāta* has recognised the influential personality and value of the works of *Mankhali Gośāla* by including his name in the list of six Teerthankaras contemporary to Buddha¹⁴. *Ṛṣibhāṣita* has gone a step further and eulogised him as *Arhat Ṛṣi*.

As such from the viewpoint of religious tolerance, the period of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is earlier than that of *Pali-Tripitaka*. This is because the growth of sectarianism sets in only after a religion becomes properly organised. *Ṛṣibhāṣita* indicates that it had been written much earlier than the beginning of sectarianism in the Jain tradition. Except the first *Śrutaskandha of Ācāraṅga* all the other Jain canonical works reflect sectarian views in varying degrees. This proves that, leaving aside first *Śrutaskandha of Ācāraṅga*, *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is the oldest of all Jain canonical works. Even the language and style indicate it to be a work of a period some-where between first *Śrutaskandha of Ācāraṅga* and first *Śrutaskandha of Sutrakṛtāṅga*.

The oldest work of Buddhist *Tripitaka* literature is *Sūttanipāta*¹⁵, but seven that is not as tolerant as *Ṛṣibhāṣita*. The *Tripitaka* literature refers to some of the *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, namely---*Narad*¹⁶, *Asit Deval*¹⁷, *Ping*,¹⁸ *Mañkhaliputta*¹⁹, *Sañjaya (Velatthiputta)*²⁰, *Vardhaman (Nigganthe Nātaputra)*²¹, *Kumaputta*²² etc.; but they have been considered at a lower level than Buddha. In other words these Buddhist works were also not free of sectarian bias, and as such they should be of a later period.

Many excerpts of the chapters in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* are found, with similarity in content, language, and composition, in *Sutrakṛtāṅga*, *Uttarādhyayana*, and *Daśavaikālika* of Jain tradition and *Sūttanipāta* and *Dhammapada* of Buddhist tradition. As such in terms of style of these works *Ṛṣibhāṣita* proves to be of an earlier period. It may be argued that the ideas and verses may have gone from Buddhist *Tripitak* literature and Jain *Uttarādhyayana* and *Daśavaikālika* to *Ṛṣibhāṣita*. But this is not true because the language and style of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is older as compared to that of these works; also it is much nearer to the language and style of the first *Śrutaskandhas* of *Ācāraṅga* and

Sutrakṛtāṅga. Moreover, *Ṛṣibhāṣita* has mentioned the ideas as general principles propagated by different Ṛṣi, but Buddhist *Tripitaka* literature and later Jain works have tried to include these ideas as belonging to their own respective traditions. For example philosophical cultivation has been dealt with in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*²³ twice and once in *Sūttanipāta*²⁴. Whereas in *Sūttanipāta* Buddha says that he does this type of philosophical cultivation, in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* the Ṛṣi says that whoever does this type of cultivation gets liberated irrespective of his cast and creed. Thus *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is conclusively proved to be of an earlier period than that of Jain or Buddhist works except first *Śrutaskandha of Ācārāṅga*.

Considering from the view point of language we find that *Ṛṣibhāṣita* has, to a larger extent, maintained the most ancient form of *Ardhamāgadhi Prākṛta*. For example in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, *Ātma* has been mentioned as *Āta* but in Jain *Aṅga* literature *Ātta*, *Āppa*, *Āda*, *Āya*, and other words have been used which are variations belonging to later periods. The free use of the consonant *Ta* conclusively puts this work in an earlier period than *Uttarādhyayana* as in *Uttarādhyayana* there is a tendency of avoiding this consonant. *Ṛṣibhāṣita* also abundantly uses word-forms like, *Janati*, *Paritappati*, *Gachchhati*, *Vijjati*, *Vattati*, *Pavattati*. This also confirms the antiquity of this work in context to both, subject and language.

The story of the serpent of *Agandhan* clan is found in *Uttarādhyayana*²⁵, *Daśavaikālika*²⁶ as well as *Ṛṣibhāṣita*²⁷. But examining all the three, it becomes evident that its mention in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is much older than the other two. Reason being that in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* it has been quoted just as an example so that the mendicant does not stray from his path; but in *Daśavaikālika* and *Uttarādhyayana* it has been included as an incident in the life of Rajimati and Rathnemi.

As such *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is older than *Sūttanipāta*, *Uttarādhyayana* and *Daśavaikālika*. That means it is of a period later than that of first *Śrutaskandha of Ācārāṅga* but an earlier work than all other *Ardhamāgadhi* canonical literature. Also being earlier to *Sūttanipāta* it becomes earlier to all *Pali Tripitaka*.

As regards deciding its period on the basis of the historical Ṛṣi mentioned in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, besides *Vajjiyaputta* all other Ṛṣis were either contemporary to Mahāvīra and Buddha or earlier to them. According to *Pāli Tripitaka Vajjiyaputta* was also a young contemporary of Buddha; he was nearer to Ānanda in age. The *Vajjiyaputtiya* sect also came into existence within a hundred years of Buddha's *Nirvāṇa*, which establishes that he was a young contemporary of Buddha. Accordingly, from historical viewpoint *Ṛṣibhāṣita* must have been written in the first century after *Nirvāṇa* of Buddha or Mahāvīra ; later changes in the text cannot be ruled out. In my opinion the period of its writing is not earlier than fifth century B. C. and certainly not later than third century B. C. I have not come across any evidence, within and outside the text, that may point toward its writing being outside this period.

From the angle of philosophical developments we find that it does not contain the finely developed forms of Jain or Buddhist principles. Only five fundamentals and eight *Karma* have been mentioned. It is also possible that these concepts were popular with the followers of Pārśwa and trickled into Mahāvīra's tradition from there only Concepts like *Parīṣaha* and *Kaṣāya* are certainly ancient. Even the expositions of Vātsiyaputra, *Mahākāśyap*, *Sāriputra* and other Buddhist Ṛṣi, in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* also contain the ancient Buddhist principles like *Santativāda*, *Kṣanikvāda* only. As such, from Buddhist angle also, *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is older than *Pāli Tripitaka*.

The Writing of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* :

Regarding the creation of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, Prof. Schubring and other scholars maintain that it must have been originally written in the tradition of Pārśwa, as the influence of that tradition is clearly seen in the first chapter where celibacy and non-possessiveness have been combined, as in the *Caturyam* systems²⁹. The detailed chapter of Pārśwa further confirms this inference.

Another basis of considering it to be a work of Pārśwa's tradition is that that tradition was comparatively more tolerant; it was also much closer in conduct to other sects of ascetics and *Śramaṇas*. With the

assimilation of the followers of *Pārśwa*'s tradition into Mahāvīra's tradition this work also came along and was included as a part of *Praśnavyākaraṇa Daśa* by Mahāvīra's followers.

The Separation of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* from *Praśnavyākaraṇa*

It now becomes obvious to ask why it was first included in *Praśnavyākaraṇa Daśa* and then separated from it. As it is purely a compilation did not find any objection in including *Ṛṣibhāṣita* in their own literature. But when the Jains formed an organised society with an independent tradition, it must have become difficult to include the monks of other tradition into their own ranks. In my opinion the separation of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* from *Praśnavyākaraṇa* was not accidental but with a purpose. It was not possible to preserve their exposition at one end and at the other criticise and demean *Mañkhaligośāla* in *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*. *Bhagvati*³⁰ and *Upāsakadaśāṅga*³¹; and Nārada in *Jñātadharma*.³² by first century A. D., to keep Jain faith intact had become the primary task. It became difficult to accept the works of Nārada, Mañkhali Gośāla, Yājñavalkya, Sāriputra etc. as the canonical expositions of *Tirthaṅkaras*; still, credit goes to Jain *Ācāryas* for safe keeping of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* as a work of anthology in spite of its being excluded from *Praśnavyākaraṇa*. Also, in order to maintain its authenticity it was accepted as expositions by omniscients out of Jain tradition. The sectarian system, however, propagated that the persons named as Pārśwa, Vardhaman, Mañkhaliputra, etc. in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* were not the same as their namesakes in Jain *Āgams*.

Why the Ṛṣis of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* were called *Pratyekbuddha* ?

In the original text of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* Ketaliputra has been referred to as *Ṛṣi*; Ambada (25) as *Parivrajaka*, Ping (32), Rishigiri (34) and Shrigiri as *Brahmin (Mahan) Parivrajaka Arhat Ṛṣi*; Sāriputra as *Buddha Arhat Ṛṣi*; and all others as *Arhat Ṛṣi*. In the chapter titled *Utkat* (Utkal) the name of the expounder has not been mentioned at all, as such there is no need of an adjective. Although the appendix at the end of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*³³ and *Ṛṣimaṇḍala*³⁴ has referred to all these persons as *Pratyekbuddha*, and twenty of them as contemporary to Ariṣṭanemi, fifteen as contemporary to Parśwanātha and remaining

as contemporary to Mahāvīra; this appears to be a later addition to the text. In the original text there is no mention of them as *Pratyekbuddha*.

In *Samavāyaṅga*, however, while detailing the subject matter of *Praśnavyākaraṇa* it has been mentioned that it is a compilation of discourses of contemporary and other *Pratyekbuddhas*. As *Ṛṣibhāṣita* had been a part of *Praśnavyākaraṇa*, indirectly *Samavāyaṅga* provides the first acceptance of the Ṛṣis of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* as *Pratyekbuddhas*³⁵. It is obvious that as majority of the Ṛṣis of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* were not of Jain tradition, in order to accept their discourses, they were believed to be *Pratyekbuddhas*. In Jain as well as Buddhist tradition, *Pratyekbuddha* is a person who attains ultimate knowledge through his solitary practices commenced by his own inspiration; he neither becomes a disciple of someone nor makes disciples to form an organisation. As such a *Pratyekbuddha* is not confined within a tradition or institutional organisation, but he is a respected person in society and his preachings are considered to be authentic.

Ṛṣibhāṣita and Principles of Jainism :

A comprehensive study of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* forces us to consider whether it propagates the beliefs of Ṛṣis of other traditions or it is just a propagation of Jain beliefs in their name. A cursory glance makes one believe that only Jain beliefs have been propagated in their name. Prof. Schubring and, with his reference, Prof. Lallan Gopal have inferred that the compiler lacks authenticity in quoting the discourses of Ṛṣis and has presented them in his own way; the basis for this inference is the similarity of beginning as well as end of each discourse. This conclusion appears to be true looking at the Jain traditional terms like *Pañca Mahāvratas*, *Kaṣāya*, *Parīṣāha* etc.

For example, in the chapter of Nārada there is a mention of four ways of cleansing which is nothing but propagation of the *Caturyāma* conception of Jains. In the chapter of Vajjiyaputta the *Karma* Principles have been propagated. This Chapter confirms that life is directed by *Karma*, and attachment is the cause of sorrow. It also explains that the transition of Karma in attachment and vice versa is cyclic like

seed and plant. The cycle of *Karma* is terminated by wiping out attachment first as destruction of roots destroys leaves, flowers, and fruits of a tree. This concept of *Karma* can also be found in chapters 13, 15, 24 and 30 of *R̥ṣibhāṣita*. Similar details are also available in Jain tradition in the thirty second chapter of *Uttarādhyayana*.

Similarly, the third chapter of Asit Deval in *R̥ṣibhāṣita* contains the concept of sin being same as adhesive; this concept is popular in Jain tradition having a particular mention in *Ācāraṅga*. This chapter also contains the mention of *Pañca Mahāvratā*, four *Kaṣāya* as well as eighteen sins from *Himsā* to *Mithyādarśana śalya*. Also included is the form and details of *Mokṣa* which is *Shiv*, *Atul*, *Amal*, *Avyaghat*, *Apurnabhava*, *Apunaravrata* and *Shashvat*. Similar description of *Mokṣa* is available elsewhere in Jain canonical literature. The mention of *Pañca Mahāvratā* and four *Kaṣyāya* can be found in many chapters of *R̥ṣibhāṣita*.

This ninth chapter of *Mahākāṣyap* contains details of *Punya*, *Pāpa*, *Samvara*, and *Nirjarā*. This chapter mentions *Kaṣyāya* also. In the ninth chapter, while discussing inflow of *Karma*, the causes have been named as *Mithyātva Dṛṣṭi*, *Pramāda*, *Kaṣyāya*, and *Yoga*; which is similar to that in the Jain tradition. It also contains many Jain traditional words like *Upakarma*, *Bāddha*, *Śpriṣṭha*, *Nikachit*, *Nirjirna*, *Siddhi*, *Śailesi Avasthā*, *Predaśodaya*, *Vipākodaya*, etc. The concept of the soul being eternal and transitory, the form of *Siddha* stage and the process of bondage and shedding of *Karma*, mentioned in this chapter are same as those in Jain philosophy.

Similarly the concepts of *Dravya*, *Kṣetra*, *Kāla*, and *Bhāva* are also found in many chapters. The twelfth chapter of *Yājñavalkya* talks about process of *Gocari* and *Śuddhaiṣaṇa* which are same as in Jain tradition. “Soul is the doer of *Karma* and sufferer of consequences bad or good,” has been mentioned in the fifteenth chapter of *Madhuryan*. The seventeenth chapter of *Vidur* contains mention of *Savadyayog Virati* and *Samabhava*. Nineteenth chapter of *Aariyayana* refers to *Ārya Jñāna*, *Ārya Darśana*, and *Ārya Cāritra* which are akin to *Samyak Jñāna*, *Samyak Darśana* and *Samyak*

Cāritra. The twenty second chapter emphasises the predominance of male in the field of religion and demeans female which is same as in the *Itthiparinna* chapter of *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*.

In the twentythird chapter of *Ramaputta*, just like *Uttarādhyayana* (28-35), topic about seeing through *Darśana*, detachment, three disciplines, and dissolution of eight types of *Karma* is a speciality of Jainism. Again, there is mention of *Jñāna*, *Darśana*, and *Cāritra* in the twenty fourth chapter. The same chapter also includes the four *Gatis* namely, *Deva*, *manuṣya*, *Tiryanca* and *Nāraka*. The twenty-fifth chapter titled *Ambad* discusses four *Kaṣāya*, four *Vikatha*, five *Mahāvratā*, three *Gupti*, discipline of five senses, six life forms, seven fears, eight prides, nine *Brahmacaryas* and ten places of meditation. This chapter also discusses the six reasons for eating which are also found in *Sthānāṅga* (Stha-6). It may be noted that although *Ambad* has been mentioned in Jain Canons as a *Parivrajaka*, it has been said that he respected *Mahāvira*³⁶; that is the reason that this chapter contains maximum number of Jain concepts.

In the twentysixth chapter of *R̥ṣibhāṣita* the description of *Brahmin* has been included just like that in twentyfifth chapter of *Uttarādhyayana*. Same chapter also mentions *Kaṣāya*, *Nirjarā*, six life forms and compassion towards all living. In the thirtyfirst chapter of *Pārśwa* we again come across *Caturyāma*, *Aṣṭavidha-Karma Granthi*, *Cār Gati*, *Pañcāstikāya* and *Mokṣa Sthāna*. This chapter, like Jain concepts, conveys that living being moves upwards and matter downwards. However, the presence of Jain concepts in this chapter is not out of place because *Pārśwa* has been accepted as one belonging to Jain tradition.

Lately, scholars have started believing that the knowledge of Jains has been inherited from the tradition of *Pārśwa*. *Schubring* has also recognised the influence of *Pārśwa* tradition of *R̥ṣibhāṣita*. Again the thirtysecond chapter of *Ping* propogates the liberation of four *Varnas* just like the Jain belief, The thirtyfourth chapter also contains discourses about *Parīṣahand Upasarga*. This chapter also discusses the liberation of monk indulging in five *Mahāvratā*, free of *Kaṣāya*,

free of attachment and inflow of *Karma*. Thirtyfifth chapter of *Uddālak*, once again, contains mention of three *Gupti*, three *Danda*, three *Ralya*, four *Kaṣāya*, four *Vikatha*, five *Samiti*, *Pañcendriyasanyam*, *Yogasandhan*, *Navakoti Parishuddha*, details of different clans free of ten *Doṣa*, acceptance of eatables prepared for others, cold and lifeless. The same chapter also mentions *Saṅgya* and 22 *Paridhaha*.

Thus, we observe that *Ṛṣibhāṣita* contains many Jain Concepts. It is natural to questions if the Jain *Ācāryas* have compiled their own concepts in the name of the *Ṛṣi* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* or the concepts were originally of these *Ṛṣi* and percolated into Jain tradition. It is evident that leaving aside Pārśwa and Mahāvīra, all other *Ṛṣi* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* were either independent ascetics or belonged to traditions other than Jain. Some of them, however, can be found in *Uttarādhyayana* and *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*. If we conclude that the concepts do not belong to the *Ṛṣi* named, the authenticity of the work and its compiler becomes doubtful. On the other hand, to accept that all these concepts that all these concepts came to Jains from other traditions is also not satisfactory. So we proceed first to examine if the concepts mentioned in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* are of the *Ṛṣi* named or of Jain *Ācāryas*.

Question of Authenticity of Concepts preached in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*

Although all the concepts and related literature of all the *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* are not available in traditions other than Jain, still, concepts and thoughts of many are available in other traditions, even today. Yājñavalkya is mentioned in *Upniṣads*, Vajjiyaputta, Mahākāśyap, and Sāriputta can be found in Buddhist *Tripitaka* literature. Similarly, Vidur, Narayan, Asit Deval etc. find place in *Mahābhārata* and other works of Hindu tradition. By comparing their ideas mentioned in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* with other sources we can evaluate their authenticity.

In eleventh chapter of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, the discourse of Mañkhali Gośāla are compiled. *Bhagwati Sūtra* and *Upāsakdaśāṅga* of Jains; *Suttanipata* and *Samañña Mahāfal Sūta* in *Dīghnikāya* of Buddhists; and 177th chapter of *Śāntiparva* in *Mahābhārata* of Hindus are other works where Mañkhali Gośāla or Mañkhiṛṣi has been mentioned. All

the three sources tell him to be a supporter of *Niyativāda*. His discourses in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* also contain indirect refernces to *Niyativāda*. It is stated in this chapter that he who trembles, feels pain, is irritated, hurt, moved, inspired by seeing the transformation in matter is not detached. A detached one does not have all these effects of seeing the transformation of matter. This is an indirect confirmation of *Niyativāda* in relation to the transformation of matter. The world has its own movement and parameters according to which it continues to move. A mendicant should look at and understand this movement, but should not be influenced by that.

The basic philosophical teaching of *Niyativāda* ought to be that one should only remain as a witness in the eventful movement of this world, In this manner this chapter reflects only the basic philosophical teachings of Gośāla. On the other hand the description of the principle of Mañkhali Gośāla. On in Jain and Buddhist literature is in fact a distorted inference. The author of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is, in fact, much more authentic than the authors of *Tripitaka* and later Jain canons.

The preachings of Mañkhi *Ṛṣi* of 177th Chapter of *Śāntiparva* in *Mahābhārata* confirms *Niyativāda* on one hand and preachings of detachment on the other. This chapter mainly preaches spectator's uninvolved attitude and detachment from the world. It preaches detachment through *Niyativāda* only. The world has its own system of movement and man cannot convert it to suit his needs, as such he should become detached by maintaining an attitude of uninvolved witness. The uniqueness of this chapter of *Mahābhārata* is that accepting Mañkhi *Ṛṣi* as supporter of *Niyativāda*, he have been believed to be proceeding towards detachment through his *Niyativāda*.

On this basis it can be concluded that the preachings of Mañkhaliputra available in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* are authentic.

Similarly preachings of Mahākāśyap are compiled in 9th chapter and Sāriputta in 38th chapter; both are connected with Buddhist tradition, When we contemplate the ideas expressed in these chapters the presence of basic tenets of Buddhism becomes clearly evident. The discourses of Mahākāśyap first of all deals with the sorrows of

the world. At the root of all sorrows is *Karma* and at the root of *Karma* is birth itself. This is just a form of *Pratitya Samutpāda* of Buddhism.

Another speciality in this chapter is the mention of *Santānvāda* while propagating the *Karma* principle; *Santānvāda* is one of the basic principles of Buddhism. In order to explain the concept of *Nirvāṇa* the metaphor of lamp (*Deepak*) has been used; this is a popular and basic metaphor from Buddhism. The whole discourse preaches detachment through *Santānvāda* and *Karmasamskāra*. This makes us conclude that this chapter contains seedlings of Buddhism.

Similarly, 38th chapter of Sāriputta contains basic tenets of Buddhism in the form of *Madhyama Mārga*. Alongwith is mentioned the *Prajñānvāda* of Buddha. It has been mentioned in this chapter that a monk can meditate conveniently with the availability of desired living quarters, bed and eatables, Still the wise should not crave for mundane things. Same is the discipline of Buddha and so this chapter too presents the preachings of Buddha with authenticity.

Same is the story about the 12th chapter, where the original preachings of Yājñavalkya have been included. Besides *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, Yājñavalkya finds mention in *Upaniṣads* and *Mahābhārata*³⁷. In *Upaniṣada*, alongwith the dialogue between Yājñavalkya and Maitreyi is mentioned their desire towards *Sannyas*. In *Ṛṣibhāṣita* also Yājñavalkya preaches getting rid of wordly desires and desire for wealth, he also mentions that both of these are intertwined and inseperable. As such, knowing these both one should tread the *Gopath* not *Mahāpath*. It appears that *Gopath* is the path of detachment and *Mahāpath* is the path of attachment; Yājñavalkya seems to be preaching the path of detachment.

It is worth pondering if the development of the *Hīnayāna* and *Mahāyāna* concepts of Buddhism is not merely the evolved form of this concept of *Gopath* and *Mahāpath*. *Mahāyāna* word is also found in *Ācārāṅga*. In the chapters 310 to 318 of *Śāntiparva* in *Mahābhārata* are compiled the preachings of Yājñavalkya. This mainly expounds the *Sāṃkhya* and *Yoga* concepts. This chapter of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* also talks about the procedure of collecting alms by a monk, which is similar

to the Jain method. Still this can be said that the author of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* has not distorted the basic preachings of Yājñavalkya.

In the twentieth chapter of *Utkate*, *Bhautikavāda* or *Cārvāka Darśan* has been propogated. Although there is no mention of the author of this chapter it is certain that the ideas of *Cārvāka* have been propounded with complete authenticity. The perachings of Vardhamān available in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* are found in almost exact similarity in the chapter titled *Bhāvana* of second *Śrutaskandha* of *Ācārāṅga* and 32nd chapter of *Uttarādhyayana*.

On the aforesaid evidences we may conclude that generally the preachings of various *Ṛṣis* have been presented authentically . However, mainly it contains only the meditational and moral aspects without any emphasis on philosophical background. This is also true that its presentation and writing has been done by Jain *Ācāryas*; and so it is natural that some concepts of Jains reflect predominantly in this work. Also there is enough evidence that what we today consider as Jain concepts, could orginally have been concepts belonging to other traditions creeping in later into Jainism. As such the authenticity and orginality of the preachings of *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* cannot totally be set aside. At the most we may deduce that there is an indirect influence of Jain tradition over them.

The historic background of *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*

It is clearly established that most of the *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* were not connected with Jain tradition. The adjectives like *Brahmin Parivrājaka* indicate that they were from non-Jain traditions. Also, some names like Dev Nārad, Asit deval, Āṅgiras Bhardvāj, Yājñavalkya, Bahuk, Vidur, Tharishen Kṛṣṇa, Dvaipāyan, Āruni, Uddālak, Nārāyan have been popular in Vedic tradition and their teachings are intact in *Upaniṣada*, *Mahābhārat*, and *Purāṇas* even today. The names of Dev Nārad, Āṅgiras Bharadvāj, Dvaipāyan also find their mention in *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, *Aupapātika*, *Antkṛtādaśā* besides *Ṛṣibhāṣita* in Jain Tradition as also in Buddhist *Tripitaka* literature.

Similarly, Vajjiyaputra, Mahākaśyap, and Sāriputra and famous personalities of Buddhist tradition and are mentioned in *Tripitaka* literature. Mañkhaliputra, Rāmputta, Ambad (*Ambashta*), Sañjaya (Velatṭhiputra) are names which belong to ‘independent Śramaṇa traditions and their mention can be found both in Jain and Buddhist traditions. Prof. C. S. Upasak, in his article “*Isibhāṣiyam and Pali*” of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* who have been mentioned in Buddhist literature. This article is being published in *Pt. Dalsukh Malvania Abhinandan Granth*. Pārśwa and Vardhamāna are the famous, twenty third and twenty fourth *Tīrthan̄karas* in Jain tradition *Ārdrak* is found in *Sūtrakṛtāṅga* besides *Ṛṣibhāṣita*. Besides these, Valkalchiri, Kurmaputra, Ketaliputra, Tetaliiputra, Bhayali, Indranāg are names most of whom are mentioned in *Isimandala* and other Jain works. Valkalchiri and Kurmaputra etc. are also mentioned in Buddhist tradition. However, even those who are neither mentioned in Jain nor Buddhist tradition, cannot be termed as fictitious.

On looking at the complete list of *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* we find that only Some, Yama, Varuna, Vayu, and Viashraman are such names which may be said to be fictitious because they have been accepted only as *Lokpalas* in the Jain, Vedic, and Buddhist traditions. But even out of these *Vāyu* has been mentioned as a *Ṛṣi* in *Mahābhārata*. Yama has been said to be the father of Yamadagni *Ṛṣi* in *Āvaśyaka Cūrni*. The possibility of Yama being a *Ṛṣi* cannot completely be ruled out, although even *Upaniṣads* have described Yama as *Lokpala*. This is certain that he was a preacher, as the dialogue between Yama and Nachiketa is well known in *Upaniṣadic* tradition. Varuna and Vaiśramaṇa have also been accepted as preachers of *Mantras* in Vedic tradition. It is possible that till the writing of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* Soma, Varuna, and Vaiśramaṇa were recognised as preachers and that is why their discourses were included in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*.

Thus, we may conclude that excepting four or five monks all the other *Ṛṣis* of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* actually existed during prehistoric and historic periods, and are not just fictitious characters.

I would only like to conclude that *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is a valuable work not only of Jain tradition but also of the Indian tradition as a whole. The religious tolerance of Indian thought is truly reflected in this work. It also has a historical importance because it provides valuable and authentic information about many known and some unknown *Ṛṣis* and their preachings. The Jain *Ācāryas* have done a valuable service to Indian literature and culture by preserving this work. In fact this work is an undeniable proof of historical existence of many Indian *Ṛṣis* of the period between 10th and 5th century B.C.

The Language of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*

Prof. Schubring has done a detailed analysis, in his preface, about the form of language and style of verses of *Ṛṣibhāṣita*. He has also discussed the text variations available in the existing manuscripts, and such neither an elaborate commentary on this matter is necessary nor do I consider myself an authority on that subject. Still I feel the need of rediting of the original text edited by Prof. Schubring, from the view point of language.

As far as the language of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is concerned, it is the ancient form of *Ardhamāgadhi*, the similarity of which with Sanskrit is evident at places. According to the antiquity of language, it can be placed somewhere between first *Śruta-skandha* of *Ācārāṅga* and *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, *Uttarādhyayana*. Whereas, an influence of Mahārāṣtri Prākṛta. Although, at some places, word forms appear to be influenced by Mahārāṣtri Prākṛta, proper study reveals that this influence must have come only through the mistakes of transcribers. For example, out of the forty-five chapters in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* forty three contain the word *Buiyam* or *Buitam*. Out of these forty three thirty six mention *Uitam* and only seven mention *Buiyan*. Certainly, the word form *Buiyam* conveys the influence of Mahārāṣtri. But it is not logical that the original author would use the form *Buitam* in thirty six must have inadvertently come due to the carelessness of the

For example, out of the forty-five chapters in *Ṛṣibhāṣita* forty three contain the word *Buiyam* or *Buitam*. Out of these forty three thirty six mention *Uitam* and only seven mention *Buiyan*. Certainly,

the word form *Buiyam* conveys the influence of Mahārāṣtri. But is not logical that the original author would use the form *Buitam* in thirty six must have inadvertently come due to the carelessness of the transcribers and influence of Mahārāṣtri on them. Same is the case of *Jadha* and *Jaha*, *Mossikar* and *Mūsiya*, *Tati* and *Tai*, *Dhaota* and *Dhooyam*, *Loye* and *Loge*. At the end of fortieth chapter *Jaha* and *Jadha* have been used in same line (*Jaha Balam Jadha Vīrayam*). Certainly, such use would not be to the liking of the author; this variation must have come due to passage of time.

Also, whereas in the third, twentyfifth, and fortyfifth chapters, use of only the *Jadha* form is seen, in the ninth, twelfth, twentysecond and twentyeighth chapters the word *Jaha* has been used. As such the question with a consideration is that, was the original form in different chapters retained during compilation? Or these variations are due to later influences. Generally speaking, *Ṛṣibhāṣita* contains the use of first person like *Pabhasati*, *Jayati*, *Meghati*, *Hinsari*, *Jevati*, *Vindati*, *Vijjati*, *Chindati*, *Seedati*, *Visujjhati*, *Vassati*, *Sinchati*, *Luppati* etc., and the tendency of omitting the last consonant, like in Mahārāṣtri Prākṛta is not seen. In the whole *Ṛṣibhāṣita* the omission of the last consonant is not seen except at eight or ten places.

Similarly the use of the sound 'Ya' instead of 'Ta' is negligible. Generally, complete *Ṛṣibhāṣita* predominantly uses the sound 'Ta'. For *Ātma*, leaving aside one or two instances, everywhere the word 'Āta' has been used. In the tenth chapter the word *Tetaliputta* has been used at places, and not *Teyaliputta* as in *Jñātadharmā-Kathā*. Similarly in the same chapter *Mūsikaridhūta* word has been used for his wife. However, at one place *Dhūyam* word has also been used. It is clear that these exceptions from later Mahārāṣtri forms must have crept into the editions of original text due to later influence. It is possible that when palm leaf copies of this work were done, these changes must have come due to the influence of the language of that period through the scribes.

Although this influence of Mahārāṣtri Prākṛta on *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is not more than two percent, the same influence on the *Ardha Māgadhi*

canons like *Ācārāṅga*, *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, *Uttarādhyayana* and *Daśavaikālika*, Supposed to be ancient, is approximately fifteen to twenty five percent. However, one reason for this may be that whereas *Uttarādhyayana* and *Daśavaikālika* were in more popular use, *Ṛṣibhāṣita* was not much in use. As a result, the effect of changed pronunciations must have been less on *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, and because of others being more in use, this effect on them must already have set in even before the palm leaf copies were made, after the last vocal rendering. Unfortunately, at the time of editing of the canons these facts were not considered and efforts to retain the oldest form of language was not made.

I feel that the old manuscripts of ancient *Ardhamagadhi* works like *Ācārāṅga*, *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, *Uttarādhyayana*, *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, *Kalpasūtra* and others should be collected and if any manuscript contains old text form, it should be preserved. Not only this, where there are variations like *Āta* and *Āya*, *Jadha* and *Jaha*, *Loye* and *Loge* in the same line, only the old forms should be accepted. It is a matter of contentment that some scholars like professors Madhusudan Dhaki and K. R. Chandra and others have drawn attention in this direction. I am hopeful that in the future editions of the canons, these facts will be attended to. As the lingual form of a book is very much helpful in determining its period, this is the responsibility of scholars that oldest form of the language of the work is retained.

On a comparative study we find that many works and parts of verses and prose of *Ācārāṅga*, *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, *Uttarādhyayana* *Daśavaikālika* and *Jñātadharmakathā* are also available in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*. But the comparative study of the language forms of these reveals that from the view point of language the text of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* is older. For example, a comparative study of *Tetaliputta* chapter of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* and *Teyaliputta* chapter of *Jnata* reveals that the language of *Ṛṣibhāṣita* has predominance of the sound 'Ta' and is older. Similarly in *Ācārāṅga*, *Sūtrakṛtāṅga*, *Uttarādhyayana* and *Daśavaikālika*, whereas 'Āya' word has been used for *Ātma*, in *Ṛṣibhāṣita*, except one or two places, the 'Āta' form has been used. This confirms its antiquity.